

PROTOCOL FOR THE SYSTEMATIC OBSERVATION OF PARENTAL BEHAVIOR DURING PRIVATE INTERACTIONS BETWEEN A FATHER OR MOTHER AND THEIR SON OR DAUGHTER (SITUATION 3) (SITUATION 3)

Once families have authorized their child's participation, a schedule is established for the play/observation sessions. For each session, a group of four children is invited to participate in play activities. The group may also consist of three to five children, depending on the final number attending. Each child is accompanied by a family member—their parent or another close relative.

The sessions are divided into four parts: 1) the children participate in a structured activity; 2) the children participate in a free activity; 3) the family member tells their child what they observed while the child was playing; 4) the family members complete several questionnaires. While one family member is in another room with the principal investigator, the rest of the family members remain in the playroom completing questionnaires.

These sessions are conducted at two points: (a) before the start of the parent training sessions (Pretest) and (b) after the family members have completed their participation in the nine workshop sessions (Posttest). These play/observation sessions are video recorded, except for the moment when the family members complete the questionnaires.

Two researchers are present in the playroom. Researcher 1 interacts with the children during structured and free play activities (situations 1 and 2), and Researcher 2 is responsible for ensuring everything runs smoothly during the play/observation session. A third member of the research team, located in an adjacent room, is responsible for instructing each parent to speak privately with their child about what happened during the play sessions (situation 3: family interaction with the child).

Situation 1. Structured activity

- By structured activity, we mean any activity with clear, known rules. However, the researcher will remind them of these rules before starting the game. The chosen activity is a board game, specifically the game of Goose. Family members are also present in the room, seated about 2-3 meters from the table where the children are playing. Magazines are available for the family members if they wish to be distracted.
- Researcher 1 welcomes the children and their families and shows them where to stand. Once all the children are gathered, the researcher explains what they will be doing and reminds them of the rules of the game. When the game is over, the researcher moves 1-2 meters away from the game table and observes the children, interacting with them only if deemed necessary (see instructions for the free play situation).

Investigator 2 gives the following instructions to the family members:

The children will play (name of game) for 8-10 minutes, and then we will let them choose any game they want from among all the ones we have prepared on the other side of the room. During all this time, “ ***You Do what you think is best to help your son or daughter make friends and get along with other children .*** ” (If any family member asks questions, the answer is "what you think is best...").

Situation 2. Free activity

- Once the structured activity has finished, the free activity phase begins. This second phase lasts between 22-25 minutes. Eight to ten board games have been prepared beforehand on nearby side tables (there was a bit of everything: memory , tower building with wooden sticks, regular puzzles , balloon-shaped puzzles , Parcheesi, card games like Uno, even two-player games like Connect Four or Battleship, etc.).

- Researcher 1 gives the following instructions to the children:

"Here are a lot of games. You can choose whichever one you want and put it on the table to play" (this way the space is restricted and recording is made easier).

- Researcher 1 stays a couple of meters away from the children and only intervenes: 1) if they ask how to play, 2) to remind them of a rule of the game, 3) to tell them they can play whatever they want; 4) to tell them to return to the table if they move away and/or remain outside the camera's field of vision; 5) if some children hit or insult each other; 6) 30 minutes after the start of the structured game, the researcher ends the game and thanks them for behaving so well.

Family members complete the questionnaires

- When the free activity phase ends, researcher 3 invites a parent to accompany them and their child to the next office, saying it will only be for 10 minutes. Afterward, they accompany them back to the playroom. Upon arriving at the playroom, they ask another parent and their child to accompany them to the interview room.
- Researchers 1 and 2 remain in the room with the children and other family members. Researcher 1 tells the children *they can continue playing whatever they like and to let them know if they need anything* . Meanwhile, Researcher 2 has set up tables for the families to fill out the questionnaires. They distribute the questionnaires and explain how to complete them, offering their assistance if needed.
- Neither researcher 1 nor researcher 2 makes any comment about the interview.

Situation 3. Interaction of a father or mother with their son or daughter

- When the free activity phase is over, researcher 3 addresses the families and says:

“Please, one of you and your child can accompany me to the office next door. It will only take 10 minutes. Afterward, you will return to the room and answer the questionnaires that the other family members are completing. While this parent is answering the questionnaires, I will meet with a second family and their child. And then with the third and fourth families. In total, it will not take more than 30 minutes .”

- Once seated in the office, the family member is informed again that the scene will be recorded. Once the family member gives their consent, they are told.

“Now I would like you to talk to your son/daughter [give them feedback —give them your opinion] about your child's behavior during play , especially regarding their social skills, in the way that will best help you make friends and get along with other children .”

- If the parent's intervention is very short, less than two minutes, the parent is encouraged to continue talking to their child.
- feedback session with the child, Researcher 3 thanks both of them and tells them not to discuss anything that happened during the interview with the other family members or the children. They then accompany the family member to the playroom so the family member can complete the questionnaires and the child can play with the other children or with Researcher 1. If the family member has finished the questionnaires before the interview, Researcher 3 thanks them for their participation and tells them they can leave or say goodbye to the other family members and children if they wish.

